

permselectivity is established. The range of concentrations over which these three membranes register reasonably satisfactory results at 1:3 ratio are shown in table 1 and represented graphically (fig. 1 and 2) with a typical membrane AVS-3T.

TABLE 1.—THE VALID RANGE OF ACTIVITIES OF NERNSTIAN RESPONSE FOR THE THREE DIFFERENT MEMBRANES AT THE 3 : 1 RATIO OF MEASUREMENT.

Ions	Activity Range
Cl ⁻	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 72.9 \times 10^{-8}$
Br ⁻	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 72.9 \times 10^{-8}$
I ⁻	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 72.9 \times 10^{-8}$
NO ₃ ⁻	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 72.9 \times 10^{-8}$
BrO ₃ ⁻	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 24.3 \times 10^{-8}$
IO ₃ ⁻	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 24.3 \times 10^{-8}$
SO ₄ ⁻²	$0.1 \times 10^{-3} - 8.1 \times 10^{-8}$

Fig. 1. Range of Nernstian response of AVS-3T membrane for Cl⁻; Br⁻ and I⁻ at 3 : 1 ratio ○—Cl⁻; △—Br⁻; ×—I⁻.

Fig. 2. Range of Nernstian response of AVS-3T membrane for univalent and bivalent ions at 3 : 1 ratio ○—NO₃⁻; △—BrO₃⁻; ×—IO₃⁻; ◊—SO₄⁻².

The range of the bivalent ion SO₄⁻² (vide figure 2 and Table 1) is much lower than that of monovalent ion, Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻. This may be due to the reduction in the membrane charge by adsorption of opposite ions on the surface^{2,13}. In case of monovalent anions the concentration range over which the Nernst potential is obeyed is more or less the same for Cl⁻, Br⁻ and I⁻ ions, except at higher activity range between 24.3×10^{-8} to 72.9×10^{-8} where the following sequence is obeyed, I⁻ > Br⁻ > Cl⁻. This may be due to the increase in the membrane charge in case of iodide ion by any adsorptive effect besides the coulombic binding and this possibility has been discussed in an excellent manner by Gregor¹⁴. Much lower range in case of BrO₃⁻ and IO₃⁻ ions may well be explained by the substantial increase in the

pore volume by these large hydrated ions and hence the reduction in the membrane charge (loc.cit) which enhances the co-ion transfer particularly the mobile ion like K⁺, at higher concentration.

From the viewpoint of TMS equation the major cause of the difference between the actual membrane potential values and those of theoreticals at higher concentration of electrolytes irrespective of mono- and bi-valent ions, is due to gross changes of the transport numbers within the membranes owing to co-ion transport and thus failing of the Donnan exclusion phenomena. Though the deviations at the dilute ranges are not too easy to explain but one may seek for the cause in the phenomena of membrane hydrolysis suggested by Scatchard¹⁵. If the transport number is calculated from the membrane potential data it is seen that *t₋* of any anion is nowhere equal to unity throughout the range studied. This occurs even in case of any ideally permselective membrane, which may be due to water transport. A more important factor which has been ignored in the TMS equation is the difference of solvent (water) activities on the two sides of the membrane and hence the influence of water transfer has been neglected.

From the detailed discussion regarding the water transport mentioned by earlier workers¹⁵⁻¹⁸, it is presumed that greater the difference in water activities on the two sides of the membrane, the larger will be the deviation due to water transport particularly with the membranes having less flow resistance¹⁹. With a view to this idea the concentration potentials have also been measured in a different way.

The e.m.f.s are measured by interposing the membranes between the same standard solutions, where the activity of an ion on one side of the membrane is kept fixed and the activity of that on the other side is changed so that the ratio gradually increases viz. 1:9, 1:27, 1:81 and so on but the upper and the lower limits are always within the range of Nernstian response as observed from the earlier measurements with fixed activity ratio 1:3. The graphical representations should yield straight lines passing through the origin having slope values in ideal cases either 59.0 mv. in case of univalent or 29.5 mv. in case of bivalent ions. Figures 3 and 4 represent the observations (shown by the symbols), where e. m. f. s are plotted against $\log \frac{a_1}{a_2}$ keeping *a₂* constant with a typical membrane AVS-3T. The presumption of water transport seems to be justified by the deviations from the theoretical slope values, observed with increase in the *a₁/a₂* ratio.

The theoretical (shown by the dotted lines) and experimental values almost coincide upto certain range and afterwards the deviations start which indicate that as the concentration or activity on the two sides of the membranes differs widely the amount of deviation from ideal behaviour increases more and more. Though the nature of deviations in all cases are the same but their magnitudes vary depending on the nature of the ion.

Fig. 3. Experimental results with AVS-3T membrane (shown by symbols) showing the deviation pattern from the theoretical values when the activity ratio gradually increases. $\circ$ - I^- ; Δ - Br^- ; $\times$ - Cl^- .

Fig. 4. Experimental results with AVS-3T membrane (shown by symbols) of univalent and bivalent ions showing the deviation pattern from the theoretical values when the activity ratio gradually increases.
A - univalent $\circ$ - NO_3^- ; Δ - BrO_3^- ; $\times$ - IO_3^-
B - bivalent $\circ$ - SO_4^{2-}

TABLE 2—THE PERCENT DEVIATION FROM THE IDEAL VALUES WITH INCREASE IN THE ACTIVITY RATIO SHOWN WITH A TYPICAL MEMBRANE AVS-3T. THE FIXED ACTIVITY ON ONE SIDE OF THE MEMBRANE IS 0.0009.

Ions	Activity Ratio			
	3 : 1 (%)	9 : 1 (%)	27 : 1 (%)	81 : 1 (%)
Cl^-	<3.0	<3.0	3.4	8.8
Br^-	<3.0	<3.0	<3.0	6.9
I^-	<3.0	<3.0	<3.0	6.0
NO_3^-	<3.0	<3.0	5.0	10.0
BrO_3^-	<3.0	<3.0	6.4	12.8
IO_3^-	<3.0	<3.0	7.0	14.8
SO_4^{2-}	<3.0	4.3	14.2	-

From the table 2 it may be pointed out that (i) The increase in percent deviation from ideal permselectivity is very much gradual with the increase in the concentration difference on the two sides of the membrane.

(ii) The pattern of percent deviation follows a parallel order with the hydrated ionic size of the ions concerned.

Regarding the ions I^- , Br^- and Cl^- the deviations, upto the ratio 1:27, are more or less the same throughout i.e. within the limits of error of the Nernstian response of the membranes. But for the larger ions like NO_3^- , BrO_3^- and IO_3^- (though univalent) and the higher valent ion like SO_4^{2-} the ratio upto which the membranes give the same Nernstian response is 1:9 after which the response is otherwise. The percent deviations follow the sequence

which is more or less the same as that of hydrated ionic size.

This suggests that the hydrated ionic size of the ion plays a very important role in the water transport which seems to be the major cause for this deviation.

Also there may be other possibilities like osmotic degradation¹⁸ due to wide difference of water activities on the two sides. But it may be said that the effect, if any, seemed to be very negligible since the equilibrium was established very rapidly during the measurements and the results were reproducible within ± 0.2 mv. The development of asymmetry potential on the membrane surface and/or on the KCl-agar tips is also possible, but these effects were tried to be nullified, as far as practicable, by interchanging the solutions on the two sides and the mean values were noted within ± 0.5 mv.

The percent deviations are also shown in table 2 in connection with AVS-3T membrane.

From all these observations it is quite evident that these 'Neosepta' like membranes offer a more or less good permselectivity in the Nernstian response within a certain range of concentration of electrolytes. Their response is otherwise within the same range as the concentrations on the two sides of the membrane differ widely, particularly for the ions having larger hydrated ionic sizes though the permselectivity is maintained. The special advantages of these membranes are due to the fact that these are suitable to handle, attain rapid equilibrium and have higher operative life.

Finally, it may be mentioned as Gregor¹ has pointed out, that in order to establish a membrane electrode for its Nernstian response over a concentration range, it is always preferable to make use of more than one method, specially for the membranes having low electrical resistance.

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